

CULTURALLY RESPONSIVE TEACHING IN KARAKALPAKSTAN: BRIDGING LINGUISTIC DIVIDES THROUGH EQUITY-CENTERED PEDAGOGY

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Annotation: This article applies pedagogies of culturally responsive teaching (CRT) to the multilingual Karakalpakstan classroom, an autonomous republic in Uzbekistan. Underpinned by sociolinguistic theory and by practice in the classroom, the article discusses how the background languages, school medium, ethnic background, and gender of the students can affect English language tutoring among 14-15-year-old pre-intermediate learners. Techniques addressed in the article range through differentiated instruction, strategic code-switching, gender-sensitive group work, identity-informed materials, and fluid assessment. Effects addressed by the article relate to decreasing educational disparities among Russian- and Karakalpak-medium learners, making classrooms more inclusive and supportive of learners' identities, and challenging fixed notions about learners. A sociolinguistic framework sets learners' embodied experience and intersectional identities to the forefront of the enterprise about language pedagogy

Keywords: Culturally responsive teaching, multilingualism, sociolinguistics, equity, language education, identity-based pedagogy, Central Asia

Introduction. In today's globalized classrooms, culturally responsive teaching (CRT) is the way forward to teach diverse student linguistic and cultural profiles. In the Karakalpakstan republic, which is part of Uzbekistan, linguistic heterogeneity is compounded by historical and structural inequalities. Teaching and learning under such conditions cannot be separated from identity, access, and social capital. English teaching must therefore be tackled from a sociolinguistic view.

This is a qualitative study about CRT practices implemented in one private school in Karakalpakstan among twelve 14- and 15-year-old pre-intermediate learners to build fair, just, and enjoyable English language classes.

The research draws on Geneva Gay's (2010) description of CRT as using the other students' cultural attributes, life experiences, and frames of reference to instruct more effectively. It is underpinned by Ladson-Billings (1995) and Krashen's (1985) Affective Filter Hypothesis, which is focused on emotional and social dimensions to learning. Tirvassen (2018) is guarded against essentialized

accounts of identity and promotes dynamic, narrative constructions, while Van Booven (2018) is interested in fostering social interactional competence among the students in multicultural social worlds.

The student population was composed of Russian- and Karakalpak-medium school students. They all share Karakalpak language as their L1, but their levels vary in their proficiency in Russian in an asymmetrical way, affecting participation in-class and confidence. Those who study in Russian-medium classes showcase higher confidence level while those who study in Karakalpak-medium classes are often shy during meaning-focused speaking activities. Russian, as generally accepted to be the wider communication language, has symbolic power that affects educational resource access (Fought, 2011; Schilling, 2011).

According to Tomlinson (2001), the lesson was addressed to the different levels of the learners' proficiency. For instance, low-level learners (Student A) were supported by the employment of visuals and sentence frames, while high-level learners (Student B) were provided with debate-based tasks. This reduced affective filters (Krashen, 1985) and encouraged all the learners to take part.

With three languages, i.e., Karakalpak, Russian, and English, being common knowledge, code-switching was utilized to explain difficult concepts. Although English was spoken as the default language for teaching, strategic use of Russian and Karakalpak facilitated understanding, validating Deumert's (2011) opinion that multilingual classrooms are advantaged by flexibility in discourse.

Gender imbalance was realized in participation. For example, despite having female students like Student C who were academic performers themselves, they were reticent to participate in group discussions. Reflective exercises and rotational group assignments were utilized to facilitate equal participation, according to Schilling (2011) and Calder (2020) guidelines.

The content was localized to represent students' identity and local culture, with themes based on Karakalpak context. For reading tasks, texts about Karakalpak national holidays, the Aral Sea, Shylpiq, towns and regions of Karakalpakstan, etc. were used to raise students' engagement to the content. This aligns with Bayley and Villarreal's (2019) argument to provide greater voice to the marginalized groups in language education to allow the students to gain a sense of ownership of learning.

For the disengaged students (Student B, for instance), curricula used TED Talks, YouGlish, and subtitled videos. They encouraged receptive

multilingualism (Deumert, 2011) and offered authentic input in line with international English usage.

Classroom strategies such as think-pair-share and sentence starters were accommodating to quieter learners, as prescribed by Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development, as they provided scaffolding interactions and reduced the anxiety of performance.

Whereas learner categorization facilitated the targeting of instruction, it also threatened to oversimplify student identities. Tirvassen (2018) cautions against essentialism and urges teachers to embrace identity as fluid and dynamic. Reflexivity is crucial for CRT practitioners to ensure that they do not unwittingly reinforce stereotypes.

Evaluation in CRT Rubrics for writing, speaking, reading, and listening, which emphasized effort, progress, and clarity over correctness, were used in formative assessments. Materials selected were well picked to avoid cultural bias as much as possible. According to Van Booven (2018) and Tirvassen (2018), assessment should not just consider linguistic accuracy but also the learners' sociocultural and interactive abilities.

Conclusion. Teaching in multilingual classrooms, such as in Karakalpakstan, is not just teaching content in languages—instead, it is a work in fostering equity, responsiveness, and identity-focused pedagogy. Teachers must transform content, recognize multilingual assets, and create spaces where everybody can be seen and heard. According to Canagarajah (1999), critical pedagogy is about challenging hegemonies and forging inclusive professional communities through validating learners' backgrounds.

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